

Large language models for automated grading in geotechnics

Enrico Soranzo

Department of Civil Engineering and Natural Hazards, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, Vienna, Austria

Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this study is to explore the application of automated grading systems in geotechnics using large language models (LLMs) and cosine similarity for enhanced assessment and educational content generation. By training and testing LLMs on synthetic and real student data, the study seeks to develop robust systems for grading technical reports and open-ended questions, aligned with industry standards. Additionally, it aims to enhance student learning through auto-grading, immediate feedback and content generation, while addressing ethical considerations such as data privacy and fairness. Ultimately, the study strives to demonstrate the potential of LLMs to improve consistency, efficiency and educational outcomes.

Design/methodology/approach – The study employs a mixed-methods approach to develop and validate automated grading systems in geotechnics. Initially, correct answers were generated manually and synthetically using a generative pre-trained transformer model, with synthetic answers compared to correct ones via cosine similarity. Real student answers underwent similar evaluation. A Web-based tool was created to assess responses in real-time, providing dynamic feedback. Additionally, LLMs were fine-tuned on geotechnics textbooks and validated using synthetic and real student data. Anonymized student project reports were graded automatically, showcasing the potential and limitations of LLMs in consistent grading and educational content generation. Ethical considerations were addressed throughout.

Findings – The study demonstrated the potential of LLMs in geotechnics education by developing ML-driven systems for grading and content generation. The grading system, using cosine similarity and LLMs, provided consistent and objective assessments comparable to human graders. Immediate feedback on open-ended questions enhanced learning outcomes, enabling students to address knowledge gaps effectively. Fine-tuning LLMs with geotechnics textbooks and industry standards facilitated the generation of accurate, relevant questions and answers, further improved by retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). Data augmentation techniques enhanced model robustness, while ethical considerations, including data privacy, fairness, and transparency, ensured responsible deployment and fostered trust among stakeholders.

Originality/value – This study offers originality and value by pioneering the application of LLMs and cosine similarity for automated grading in geotechnics education, a domain with limited exploration in educational technology. By integrating RAG and fine-tuning LLMs with domain-specific textbooks, it bridges the gap between advanced machine learning techniques and practical applications in engineering education. The development of real-time feedback tools and robust grading systems enhances both student learning and instructional efficiency. Furthermore, addressing ethical considerations such as fairness and data privacy sets a precedent for responsible artificial intelligence (AI) deployment, contributing to the broader adoption of AI in academia.

Keywords Artificial intelligence, Geotechnical engineering, Education and training

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Automated grading systems using machine learning (ML) have gained attention in higher education for their potential to reduce workload and improve consistency (Stoica, 2022; Gobrecht *et al.*, 2024). These systems employ natural language processing (NLP) (Rus and Oviedo, 2013) to analyse and grade essays and programming assignments (Suresh *et al.*, 2023; Aldriye *et al.*, 2019). Recent research has demonstrated that ML-based grading can outperform human graders in terms of consistency and accuracy, with one study showing a 44% smaller median absolute error compared to human re-graders (Gobrecht *et al.*, 2024). However, challenges remain, including

the need for continuous improvement and acceptance by teaching assistants and instructors (Stoica, 2022). Additionally, some existing systems face limitations in user experience, particularly for beginner programmers and may struggle with syntax errors and language barriers (Aldriye *et al.*, 2019). Despite these challenges, ML-driven grading systems show promise in enhancing fairness and efficiency in educational assessment (Gobrecht *et al.*, 2024; Suresh *et al.*, 2023).

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Automated grading systems in engineering education offer numerous benefits for both students and instructors. These systems enable real-time continuous assessment across various activities, providing immediate feedback to students and allowing instructors to monitor student performance from the course's outset (Serrano *et al.*, 2018). They can evaluate complex tasks such as engineering drawings (Kwon and McMains, 2015), MATLAB programming assignments (Bowen, 2003) and Microsoft Excel spreadsheets and graphs (Hekman, 2019). Grading technical assignments and project reports in geotechnics can be time-consuming for instructors and teaching assistants, but automated systems can significantly reduce this workload, allowing educators to focus more on teaching and providing personalised feedback to students (Bowen, 2003). These systems can be continuously updated and improved based on new data and feedback, which is essential in a field like geotechnics where industry standards and best practices are constantly evolving. Additionally, ML-driven systems can help mitigate language barriers by focusing on the technical accuracy and content of the submissions rather than language proficiency. By fine-tuning automated grading systems using geotechnics textbooks, assessments can be aligned with current professional practices and expectations. Automated grading systems also encourage student learning by enabling more frequent assignments, self-assessment opportunities and prompt feedback (Bowen, 2003; Hekman, 2019). Additionally, these systems facilitate the analysis of common errors across the class, informing targeted instruction (Kwon and McMains, 2015).

Grading multiple-choice questions is relatively straightforward for automated systems, as it involves matching student responses to predefined correct answers. However, grading open-ended questions is significantly more challenging due to the variability in student responses and the need for nuanced understanding and evaluation of the content. This knowledge gap highlights the need for ML techniques capable of accurately assessing open-ended responses. The primary objective of this study is to explore the application of automated grading systems in the field of geotechnics, leveraging large language models (LLMs) and cosine similarity for content generation and enhanced student assessment. Specifically, the study the study seeks to:

- generate educational content by fine-tuning LLMs using geotechnics textbooks;
- develop and validate ML-driven grading systems by training and testing a LLM on both synthetic and real student data; and
- automate the grading of technical reports.

Furthermore, the study aims to enhance student learning by implementing ML to help students auto-grade their work, improve their knowledge and receive detailed and immediate feedback. Finally, the study addresses ethical and legal considerations, including data privacy, student consent and fairness in model training, to ensure the responsible deployment of these technologies. By achieving these objectives, we aim to demonstrate the potential of LLMs in generating educational content in the domain of geotechnics, automating the grading process and providing consistent and objective assessments.

2. Methodology

The study involves data collection and preprocessing, model training and validation and testing on real student answers and project reports. Most of the work has been carried out using Python (Van Rossum, and Drake, 2009), utilising its libraries and tools for NLP and ML. The computations were performed on a standard computer equipped with a GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060) to handle the intensive processing tasks efficiently.

2.1 Data generation and collection

2.1.1 Synthetic data generation

The generation of questions and answers is a critical component of this study, as it forms the basis for training and evaluating the ML-driven grading system. The process involves both manual and synthetic generation of questions and answers to create a diverse and comprehensive data set.

To generate these data, 26 geotechnics textbooks (Table 1) were fed into ChatGPT 4.0. The questions were retrieved using a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) approach. Initially, a set of 30 questions (Table A1 in Appendix) related to geotechnics was created with ChatGPT 4.0 (Chen *et al.*, 2024)

Table 1 Comprehensive dataset of 26 geotechnics textbooks used to generate questions and answers for this study

No.	Reference
1	Atkinson (2007)
2	Baecher and Christian (2003)
3	Budhu (2011)
4	Knappett and Craig (2010)
5	Das (2010b)
6	Das (2010a)
7	Das (2020)
8	Elliott (1993)
9	Fredlund <i>et al.</i> (2012)
10	Hoek (2006)
11	Hung <i>et al.</i> (2009)
12	Ishibashi and Hazarika (2015)
13	Knappett and Craig (2012)
14	Milsom (2003)
15	Murthy (2007)
16	Ng and Menzies (2007)
17	Rankine (1857)
18	Schofield and Wroth (1968)
19	Sivakugan and Das (2009)
20	Smith (2014)
21	Thompson and Jarrah Beasley (2012)
22	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Naval Facilities Engineering Command and Air Force Civil Engineer Support Agency (2005)
23	Van Baars (2018)
24	Venkatramaiah (1993)
25	Weber (2010)
26	Xiao (2015)

Note(s): These textbooks were scraped from the internet and served as the primary knowledge base for the RAG approach, ensuring that the generated content aligns with established geotechnical principles and industry standards

and checked by the authors to ensure the relevance and accuracy of the content (Section 2.2.3).

2.2 Application of retrieval-augmented generation

RAG is an advanced technique that combines the strengths of retrieval-based and generation-based models to enhance the performance of NLP tasks (Lewis *et al.*, 2020). In RAG, a retrieval component first searches a large corpus of documents to find relevant information and then a generation component uses this information to produce coherent and contextually accurate responses. This approach leverages the vast amount of knowledge stored in external documents, making it particularly useful for tasks that require detailed and specific information.

The application of RAG offers mainly two benefits for question and answer generation in geotechnics:

- 1 By retrieving information from a curated corpus of geotechnical sources, the model can generate questions and answers that are more accurate and relevant to the field. This ensures that the generated content aligns with current best practices.
- 2 One of the key advantages of RAG is its ability to provide source attribution. When generating questions and answers, the model can reference the specific documents from which the information was retrieved. This transparency enhances the credibility and reliability of the generated content.

2.2.1 Preprocessing and integration

We utilised the `requests` library to collect relevant geotechnical documents from the Web (Reitz, 2024). The textbooks were integrated into ChatGPT through the “Academic AI” system (Acomarket, 2025) that operates as a cloud-based platform designed to provide universities with access to artificial intelligence (AI) tools, while ensuring data privacy and compliance with institutional security standards. The system was developed in collaboration with Microsoft and is hosted on a dedicated instance of Microsoft Azure. A key feature of the system is its ability to enable users to create customised chatbots tailored to specific needs. This functionality was specifically developed to allow academic institutions to develop AI-driven solutions that can answer questions based on course materials, research papers or administrative documents.

2.2.2 Questions’ and answers’ generation

The geotechnical questions were designed to cover a range of topics and complexity levels within the field of geotechnics. For each question, a corresponding correct answer was also generated to serve as a reference for evaluating student responses (Table A2 in Appendix).

The tailored ChatGPT-4.0 was also employed to generate synthetic “students” answers to the questions. To overcome the limitation of the maximum number of tokens per response, the answers were generated in batches of five synthetic “students”. This process involved instructing ChatGPT-4.0 to provide answers with varying degrees of quality, including good, bad and off-topic responses. By generating 100 fictitious student answers in this manner, the data set was enriched with a wide range of answer qualities, which is crucial for training the ML-driven grading system to accurately assess and differentiate

between high-quality and low-quality responses. As an example, the answers by one synthetic “student” are shown in Table 2. The chat history is included in the manuscript as supplementary material.

2.2.3 Human inspection and validation

To ensure the quality and relevance of the generated data, human inspection was an integral part of the process. The initial set of 30 geotechnics questions was carefully reviewed by the authors to verify their accuracy, clarity and alignment with geotechnical principles. Similarly, the corresponding answers were inspected to confirm their correctness and completeness. For the synthetic student answers and their grading, the authors evaluated a representative sample to ensure that the generated responses reflected a realistic range of quality, including good, poor and off-topic answers. This rigorous validation process was essential for creating a reliable data set to train and evaluate the ML-driven grading system.

Table 2 Example of 30 ChatGPT-generated “student” answers, representing one synthetic student’s responses to the geotechnical questions

No.	ChatGPT-generated “student” answer
1	Cohesive soils retain water and are used in construction
2	The test measures water flow through soil
3	The angle is about 35 degrees
4	Consolidation happens when water leaves soil
5	UU is fast, CU is medium, CD is slow
6	The Proctor test finds the best water content for soil
7	A borehole log shows soil layers
8	FoS is the ratio of resisting to driving forces
9	Shallow foundations are for light loads, deep for heavy
10	Void ratio is voids to solids, saturation is water in voids
11	Residual soils form in place, transported are moved
12	Atterberg limits classify soil
13	SPT measures soil strength
14	Effective stress is total stress minus pore pressure
15	A flow net shows water flow in soil
16	Bearing capacity depends on soil type and load
17	Active is when soil pushes, passive is when it resists
18	Liquefaction happens in loose, saturated sands
19	The plate load test measures soil settlement
20	Geosynthetics are materials for soil reinforcement
21	Total stress is overall, effective is carried by soil
22	The critical gradient is when soil starts to move
23	Hydrometer analysis measures fine soil particles
24	The coefficient of consolidation shows how fast soil settles
25	Soil compaction increases density
26	Soil suction affects strength and permeability
27	Cantilever walls are tall, gravity walls are short
28	Pile settlement depends on soil and load
29	The vane shear test measures soil strength
30	Centrifuge tests simulate real-scale soil problems

Note(s): These answers were generated with varying degrees of quality to simulate a realistic range of student performance. This diversity is critical for training and evaluating the ML-driven grading system to differentiate between high-quality and low-quality answers effectively

2.3 Cosine similarity for answer comparison

Cosine similarity is a measure used to determine the similarity between two vectors in an inner product space. In the context of LLMs, cosine similarity is often used to compare the similarity between text embeddings, such as student answers and correct answers.

Text embeddings are numerical representations of text that capture the semantic meaning of the text. These embeddings are generated by transforming text into high-dimensional vectors. For this task, we used the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer (Face, 2024) from the Sentence Transformers library (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) to generate text embeddings. This model is a lightweight and efficient transformer model that produces high-quality sentence embeddings suitable for various NLP tasks.

The mathematical definition of cosine similarity is as follows. Given two vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , the cosine similarity is defined as:

$$\text{cosine_similarity}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{B}\|}$$

where:

- $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i$ is the dot product of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} .
- $\|\mathbf{A}\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2}$ and $\|\mathbf{B}\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}$ are the magnitudes of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , respectively.

The interpretation of the cosine similarity is as follows. A cosine similarity of 1 means that the vectors are identical; cosine similarity of 0 means the vectors are orthogonal (i.e. no similarity) and similarity of -1 means the vectors are diametrically opposed. A visual depiction of the cosine similarity is given in Figure 1 for the words “clay” and “silt”, where the cosine of the angle θ is the cosine similarity.

Figure 1 Illustration of cosine similarity in the context of geotechnical terms. The figure shows the vectors representing the words “clay” and “silt” in a high-dimensional embedding space. The cosine similarity is determined by the cosine of the angle θ between the two vectors, where a smaller angle indicates higher similarity. This concept is used to compare text embeddings, such as student answers and correct answers, to evaluate their semantic similarity

Source: Original work by the author

Consider now our task of grading student answers in a geotechnics course. Suppose we take the correct answer number 1 from Table A2 in Appendix and the corresponding “student” answer from Table 2, both represented as vectors of text embeddings generated by an LLM.

- “Correct” Answer Vector (\mathbf{A}): “Cohesive soils, such as clays, have fine particles and exhibit plasticity, while cohesionless soils, such as sands and gravels, consist of larger particles and rely on friction for strength. Cohesive soils are significant in retaining water and are prone to settlement, while cohesionless soils are preferred for drainage and stability”.
- Student Answer Vector (\mathbf{B}): “Cohesive soils retain water and are used in construction.” To compare these answers, we calculate the cosine similarity between their vectors. The cosine similarity score will indicate how similar the student answer is to the correct answer, with a score closer to 1 indicating higher similarity.

2.3.1 Optimisation of thresholds for grade prediction

The process of deriving student grades from cosine similarity scores involves optimising thresholds to align the predicted grades with those obtained through the tailored ChatGPT. The thresholds must divide the range of cosine scores into bins, with grades assigned according to the bin in which a score fell. Higher cosine similarity scores corresponds to better, i.e. lower, grades.

To optimise the thresholds, an objective function was designed to maximise the macro-averaged F_1 score, which measures the balance between precision and recall across multiple classes. The function predicted grades using the current thresholds, compared them to the manual grades and returned the negative F_1 score to facilitate minimization. The optimization was performed using the differential evolution algorithm (Storn and Price, 1997), which iteratively refined the thresholds within the range of cosine similarity scores. The algorithm ensured that the thresholds remained in increasing order and used a population-based approach to explore the solution space.

2.3.2 Interactive assessment tool for data collection

We developed an interactive assessment tool using the Streamlit framework to evaluate student responses to geotechnical questions accessible under the url <https://soranz84-carlo.hf.space> (Figure 2). This tool is provided to the students of the course “Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering” at BOKU (Soranzo and Wu, 2025). The course is taught in German.

To dynamically manage and present questions, the application retrieves data from a Google Sheet, containing questions and corresponding correct answers. These data are accessed via Google’s API using service account credentials, with the responses converted into a Pandas DataFrame for ease of processing. A caching mechanism ensures efficient data retrieval without redundant API calls.

Session state variables within the Streamlit framework maintain the current question, correct answer and similarity score (Section 2.3) across user interactions. This state management allows users to provide answers, view feedback and seamlessly transition to new questions.

Figure 2 Screenshot of the Web application for dynamic student feedback. The question “Define overconsolidation, how OCR is calculated and its influence on K_0 ” is answered with “Overconsolidation occurs when the soil experienced a higher stress in the past ($OCR = \sigma_{v,max}/\sigma_v$). K_0 increases with OCR”. The cosine similarity score and the grade achieved are 0.76 and 2, respectively, corresponding to “good” in the Austrian grading system

Bewertung geotechnischer Fragen mit Cosine Similarity

Willkommen zur **Bewertung geotechnischer Fragen!**

Dieses Tool verwendet modernste KI-Technologie, um Ihre Antworten mit den korrekten Antworten zu vergleichen.

Geben Sie Ihre Antwort ein und erhalten Sie eine Bewertung basierend auf der Ähnlichkeit.

Frage:

Definieren Sie was eine Ueberkonsolidierung ist und wie der Ueberkonsolidierungsgrad ermittelt wird (mit Formel). Erklären Sie die Auswirkung der Ueberkonsolidierung auf den Erdruhedruckbeiwert.

Ihre Antwort:

Überkonsolidierung passiert, wenn der Boden eine höhere Spannung in der Vergangenheit erfahren hat ($OCR = \sigma_{v,max}/\sigma_v$). Der Erdruhedruckbeiwert nimmt mit OCR zu.

Antwort bewerten

Ähnlichkeitswert: 0.76

Die Antwort ist **korrekt!** Note: 2

Ihre Antwort wurde in Google Sheets gespeichert!

Source: Original work by the author

When the user submits an answer, the system computes the cosine similarity between the user’s input and the correct answer. Based on the similarity score, the tool categorises the response as correct (corresponding to Grades 1 and 2 in the Austrian grading system), partially correct (corresponding to Grades 3 and 4) or incorrect (corresponding to the failing Grade 5). The cosine similarity thresholds associated with the grades are obtained according to Section 2.3.1. User responses are further logged in a separate Google Sheet for the analysis according to Section 3.2.

To facilitate a continuous assessment experience, the interface includes a “Next Question” button. This mechanism resets the current state and randomly selects a new question from the data set.

2.4 Grading with large language models

Whereas the previous approach is merely based on the similarity between given and correct answers, this section explores the use of LLMs trained on triplets of Question, Answer and Grade as a grading system. Training an open source LLM on ChatGPT enables, *de facto*, independence from third-party applications. This process can be seen as a form of “distillation,” where knowledge from a larger model (ChatGPT) is distilled into a smaller, open-source one. To do this, we graded the answers of the synthetic “students” using the tailored ChatGPT of Section 2.1.1. The answers were graded from 1 (“very good”) to 5 (“fail”) according to the Austrian system. This problem is framed as a classification task and we could have alternatively used grades such as A, B, C, D

and E. This approach provided a diverse data set to effectively train and evaluate the ML-driven grading system. Due to space constraints, the entire table is provided as supplementary material and only the first question and 5 out of 100 answers per questions, each corresponding to a different grade, are shown in Table 3.

2.4.1 Training process

The training process for our sequence classification model involves several key steps, which are detailed below. We begin by loading the data set from an Excel file using the pandas library (Wes McKinney, 2010). The data set contains columns for questions, answers and corresponding grades. The grades are mapped to integer labels and converted to the int64 data type. The data set is then converted into a format suitable for the Hugging Face datasets library (Lhoest et al., 2021).

We utilise the AutoTokenizer from the Hugging Face transformers library to tokenise the input text (Wolf et al., 2020). Specifically, we use the distilbert-base-uncased tokenizer (Sanh et al., 2019). The tokenisation function processes each example by truncating and padding the text to a maximum length of 512 tokens. Additionally, the grade labels are added to the tokenised output. The tokenised data set is created using the map function from the datasets library.

A pre-trained DistilBERT model is loaded using the AutoModelForSequenceClassification class from the Hugging Face transformers library. DistilBERT (Sanh et al., 2019) is a small, fast and efficient Transformer model with 40% fewer parameters and 60% faster inference while retaining 95% of BERT's performance (Devlin et al., 2019). The model is configured for sequence classification with five output labels, corresponding to the five possible grades. The model is then moved to the GPU.

The training configuration is defined using the TrainingArguments class. Key parameters include an output directory for saving the model, an evaluation strategy set to epoch, a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} , batch sizes of 16 for both training and evaluation, three training epochs, a weight decay of 0.01, a logging directory, logging steps set to 10 and the use of mixed precision training on GPU.

To evaluate the model's performance, we define a custom metric computation function. This function calculates accuracy, F_1 score, precision and recall using the scikit-

learn library (Pedregosa et al., 2011). The metrics are computed by comparing the predicted labels (obtained by taking the argmax of the logits) with the true labels.

The tokenised data set is shuffled and split into training and evaluation sets, with 80% of the data used for training and 20% for evaluation. The splitting is performed in a reproducible manner by setting a random seed.

The Trainer class from the transformers library is used to train the model. The training process is monitored using a progress bar provided by the tqdm library (da Costa-Luis, 2024). The model is trained for the specified number of epochs and the progress is updated accordingly.

Upon completion of training, the model and tokenizer are saved to the specified output directory. The model is then evaluated on both the training and evaluation data sets to assess its performance. The evaluation metrics are printed for further analysis. Confusion matrices are generated for both the training and evaluation data sets to provide a detailed view of the model's performance across different grade categories.

2.5 Automatic grading of technical reports

In this application, we develop a comprehensive pipeline for preprocessing, training a classification model on German text data. The text data consist of student reports concerning two geotechnical engineering applications:

- 1 the design of a foundation system for a detached building; and
- 2 the design of a levee.

The input data, such as number of floors and ground dimensions of the building or flood height and soil properties for the levee, are randomly shuffled for each student. Students are graded according to the Austrian system. The data set consists of 100 graded assignments. The assignment and grades are anonymised before training by removing direct (personal data) and indirect (unique grades) identifiers.

2.5.1 Data preprocessing

The first step in the pipeline involves cleaning and preprocessing the raw text data. We apply a series of text processing techniques to standardise the data set and prepare it for downstream tasks. Specifically, we perform the following steps:

Table 3 First ChatGPT-generated question and answers with five levels of accuracy and corresponding grades

Question	"Student" answers	Grade (1–5)
Explain the difference between cohesive soils and cohesionless soils. Provide examples of each and discuss their engineering significance	Cohesive soils are fine-grained and retain water, making them suitable for applications like clay liners, while cohesionless soils are coarse-grained and allow water to drain freely	1
	Cohesive soils are sticky and retain water, while cohesionless soils are loose and drain well	2
	Cohesive soils are impermeable, cohesionless soils are highly permeable	3
	Cohesive soils are sticky and cohesionless soils are loose	4
	I don't know	5

- *Lowercasing*: The text is converted to lowercase to remove case sensitivity and standardise the data set.
- *Special Character Removal*: Special characters are removed to focus only on relevant linguistic content. The cleaning function ensures that only letters, punctuation and numbers are retained.
- *Whitespace Normalization*: Multiple spaces and newlines are replaced with a single space to ensure consistent formatting.

After cleaning, the processed data are converted into a Hugging Face Dataset object, which facilitates efficient tokenization and model training.

2.5.2 Model training

We employ the pre-trained `dbmdz/bert-base-german-cased` model (Staatsbibliothek, 2025), which is specifically designed for German text. The model is fine-tuned on our data set, with the output layer adapted to predict one of five grade classes.

The first step in training involves tokenising the text data. Using the tokeniser associated with `dbmdz/bert-base-german-cased`, the text is converted into a format suitable for input into the transformer model. The tokeniser ensures that the text is padded to a uniform length and truncated if necessary, allowing for efficient batch processing during training.

The training process is managed using the Trainer API from Hugging Face. Key training parameters include:

- *Learning rate*: A learning rate of 2×10^{-5} is selected to balance convergence speed and stability.
- *Batch size*: A batch size of eight is used for both training and evaluation to optimise memory usage and computational efficiency.
- *Number of epochs*: The model is trained for eight epochs to allow sufficient time for convergence.
- *Weight decay*: A weight decay of 0.01 is selected.
- *Early stopping*: The best model is saved based on validation accuracy.

The optimiser used is AdamW (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2017), which is widely used for transformer-based models and the learning rate is dynamically adjusted using a linear scheduler.

To evaluate model performance, we compute:

- *Accuracy*: The proportion of correctly predicted labels.
- *Precision*: The proportion of true positive predictions relative to the total predicted positives.
- *Recall*: The proportion of true positive predictions relative to the total actual positives.
- *F₁ Score*: The weighted harmonic mean of precision and recall.

These metrics are computed using the data sets library from Hugging Face (Lhoest et al., 2021), which integrates with our training pipeline to provide detailed performance analysis. After training, the model and its tokeniser are saved to disk for future use.

3. Results

The results of grading open-ended questions using cosine similarity and a language model (LLM) are presented in Section 3.1. They also include a comparison between synthetic

answers and those provided by bachelor students (Section 3.2). Finally, the results of the test reports' grading is shown in Section 3.3.

3.1 Grading open-ended questions

3.1.1 Cosine similarity

The optimised thresholds between the grades define the following intervals:

- -1 to 0.092 for “unsatisfactory”, failing Grade 5;
- 0.092 – 0.587 for “adequate” Grade 4;
- 0.587 – 0.685 for “satisfactory” Grade 3;
- 0.685 – 0.825 for “good” Grade 2; and
- 0.825 – 1 for “very good” Grade 1.

With these intervals, a precision of 0.440, recall of 0.416, F_1 score of 0.401 and accuracy of 0.416 were achieved.

The corresponding confusion matrix is shown in Figure 3. The diagonal values of the confusion matrix indicate the true positives for each class, with the highest performance observed for Grades 4 and 2. However, performance for Grade 3s and 5 was notably lower. Misclassifications were frequent, particularly into Grade 4. This suggests a bias toward this grade. Grade 5 had the fewest true positives.

3.1.2 LLM grading

Fine-tuning the LLM on the ground truth resulted in a significant improvement in performance compared to the cosine similarity. The confusion matrices for the training and testing data sets demonstrate this improvement (Figures 4 and 5). On the training data set, the model achieved near-perfect classification, with most predictions concentrated along the diagonal of the confusion matrix. For example, Grade 2 had 879 true positives and only 11 misclassifications, while Grade 5 was perfectly classified with no errors. The confusion matrix for testing shows very few misclassifications, such as 186 true positives and only 3 errors for Grade 2, and 22 true positives with no errors for grade 5.

The metrics further highlight the model's strong performance. On the training data set, the model achieved an accuracy of 98.3% and an F_1 score of 98.3%. On the testing data set, the accuracy and F_1 score were 97.5%. These results indicate that the model generalises well, as evidenced by the small gap between training and testing performance. Compared to the cosine similarity model, the fine-tuned LLM demonstrates a dramatic improvement and a balanced performance across all classes with minimal errors.

3.2 Lecturer's grading of real answers

We provided the students with the possibility of automatic grading their answers through a Web application with cosine similarity (Section 2.3.2). The cosine similarity score was then translated into grades according to the optimal thresholds developed in Section 3.1.1. During the first semester of operation, we collected 56 student answers, which were graded automatically. Here, we assess the applicability of this automatic grading system (Section 2.4) by comparing its results with manual grading performed by the lecturer.

The comparison between automatic grading and manual grading is visualised in the confusion matrix of Figure 6 and yielded the following performance metrics:

Figure 3 Confusion matrix illustrating the performance of the grading system based on cosine similarity, with ChatGPT grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

Figure 4 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained for the training set with LLM, with ChatGPT grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

Figure 5 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained for the validation set with LLM, with ChatGPT grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

- Precision: 0.772;
- Recall: 0.527;
- F_1 score: 0.483; and
- Accuracy: 0.527.

The maximum probability, corresponding to the predicted grade, is referred to as the “confidence” of the prediction. This confidence is visualised in Figure 7, which reveals three distinct confidence groups. The highest confidence group consists of predictions with a confidence level exceeding 80%. This observation raises the question of how the model’s performance would change if only predictions from the highest confidence group were considered. To explore this, we applied an 80% confidence threshold in Figure 8. However, the results show only marginal improvement and in fact, precision decreases slightly. The updated performance metrics are as follows:

- Precision: 0.682;
- Recall: 0.611;
- F_1 score: 0.552; and
- Accuracy: 0.611.

To further illustrate the performance of the system, we present examples of both negative and positive cases. Each example includes the question, the student’s answer, the LLM-assigned grade (with confidence level) and the lecturer’s grade along with reasoning.

Negative examples

Question: Specify the filter rules of Terzaghi and explain which two functions are fulfilled by complying with these rules.

Answer: $\sigma' = \sigma - u$. Effective stress (on grains) = total stress (on total volume) – pore water pressure (water uplift).

LLM grade: 2 (95.9%)

Lecturer’s grade: 5 (the question specifically asks about the filter rules of Terzaghi and the two functions they fulfil. However, the student’s response is off-topic, as it discusses Terzaghi’s concept of effective stress instead, which is unrelated to the filter rules.)

Question: Why does a groundwater lowering often lead to settlements at the ground surface?

Answer: Since the entire body of groundwater is lowered.

LLM grade: 2 (88.2%)

Lecturer’s grade: 5 (the answer merely restates the question without providing any additional explanation or relevant information.)

Question: What is the purpose of the Proctor test?

Answer: Shear parameters and soil conditions.

LLM grade: 2 (88.1%)

Lecturer’s grade: 5 (The Proctor test is not designed to determine shear parameters, and the term “soil conditions” is overly vague and lacks specificity.)

Positive examples

Question: Explain how the stresses in the soil change with increasing depth as a result of loading.

Answer: They are increasing to a depth where they can be neglected. This is done because the stress is transmitted sideways and absorbed by the ground.

LLM grade: 2 (96.2%)

Figure 6 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained with LLM, with lecturer's grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

Figure 7 Histogram illustrating the confidence levels of the LLM-based grading system for its predictions. The confidence level represents the probability assigned to the predicted grade. The histogram is divided into three distinct confidence groups: low, medium and high confidence, with the highest confidence group exceeding 80%

Source: Original work by the author

Lecturer's grade: 2 (Although the student correctly states that stresses increase with depth, they later add that the stresses diminish “until they can be neglected,” justifying this by explaining that the stress is transferred sideways – a statement that is accurate.

However, there is a critical typo where “increase” is written instead of “decrease”. Due to this error, the assigned grade is 2)

Question: Explain the effect of the overconsolidation on the shear strength and the deformability of the soil.

Figure 8 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained with LLM, with lecturer's grades serving as the ground truth, after filtering the answers by applying the optimised confidence threshold of 0.80. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

Answer: The shear strength increases, the deformation decreases, because the soil becomes stiffer.

LLM grade: 2 (96.9%)

Lecturer's grade: 2 (the answer is generally correct; however, the explanation for the reduced deformability could be enhanced by explicitly referencing the unloading-reloading effect, which provides a more precise justification.)

Question: Why does a groundwater lowering often lead to settlements at the ground surface?

Answer: Since the entire body of groundwater is lowered, the saturation of the soil decreases, which leads to the shrinkage of the porous volume and less buoyancy of the soil.

LLM grade: 2 (83.6%)

Lecturer's grade: 2 (the answer is generally correct but lacks depth and precision, as it does not explicitly mention the role of increased effective stress due to groundwater lowering.)

3.3 Grading test reports

The performance of the dbmdz/bert-base-german-cased model on the validation set was evaluated using several metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall and F_1 score. The results are as follows:

- Accuracy: 0.714;
- Precision: 0.624;
- Recall: 0.714; and
- F_1 score: 0.656.

These results indicate that the model achieves a moderate level of performance in the automatic grading of technical reports. The accuracy of 0.714 suggests that the model correctly predicts the grades approximately 71% of the time. The precision of 0.624 indicates that around 62% of the predicted positive grades are correct, while the recall of 0.714 shows that the model identifies 71% of the actual positive grades. The F_1 score of 0.656, which balances precision and recall, reflects a reasonable level of effectiveness. The confusion matrix is presented in Figures 9 and 10 for the training and test sets.

Although the model demonstrates promising results, its performance may still be insufficient for deployment in an educational setting where high accuracy and reliability are critical. To further enhance the model's performance, improvements in data preprocessing, augmentation and training strategies are necessary. Further improvements in data preprocessing, augmentation and model training are required to enhance the model's performance. Another strategy the author plans to explore is abandoning this LLM grading approach entirely in favour of using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (O'Shea and Nash, 2015) or visual transformers (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020).

4. Ethics

The deployment of LLMs for automated grading and content generation in geotechnics raises several ethical considerations

Figure 9 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained for the training set of the test reports with LLM, with lecturer's grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

that must be addressed to ensure responsible and fair use of these technologies. This section discusses the key ethical issues, including data privacy, student consent, fairness in model training and the potential impact on education.

4.1 Data privacy and student consent

One of the primary ethical concerns in using LLMs for automated grading is the protection of student data privacy. The collection and use of student answers, project reports and other educational materials necessitate stringent measures to safeguard personal information. In this study, all real student data collected were anonymised to ensure privacy and confidentiality. Even when working with anonymised data, it is a good practice to maintain transparency with students about how their data will be used and to provide them with the option to opt-out if they do not wish to participate.

4.2 Fairness and bias in model training

Ensuring fairness in automated grading systems is essential to prevent bias and discrimination. Bias in training data can lead to unfair grading outcomes, disproportionately affecting certain groups of students. To mitigate this risk, the training data set should be diverse and representative of the student population. In this study, both synthetic and real student data were used to create a comprehensive and varied data set. Data augmentation techniques, such as synonym replacement and back-translation, can be used to enhance the data set's diversity. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the model's

performance across different demographic groups are necessary to identify and address any biases that may arise.

4.3 Transparency and accountability

Transparency in the development and deployment of automated grading systems is critical to building trust among students, educators and stakeholders. The decision-making process of the LLM should be interpretable, allowing educators to understand how grades are assigned. In this study, additionally, the use of RAG models included source attribution, enhancing the credibility and reliability of the generated content. Cosine similarity scores and probability distributions for different grades were provided to illustrate the model's confidence in its predictions. Clear documentation of the model's capabilities, limitations and potential sources of error should be made available to users.

4.4 Impact on education and student learning

The introduction of ML-driven grading systems can significantly impact education and student learning. While these systems offer the potential for consistent and objective assessments, they should complement, rather than replace, human judgment. Educators should remain actively involved in the grading process, using automated systems as tools to assist rather than dictate final grades. The use of ML to provide detailed and immediate feedback can enhance student learning by helping them understand their mistakes and improve their knowledge. However, it is essential to ensure that students do

Figure 10 Confusion matrix of the grades obtained for the validation set of the test reports with LLM, with lecturer's grades serving as the ground truth. The matrix shows the distribution of predicted grades across the five categories of the Austrian grading system. Diagonal values represent true positives, while off-diagonal values represent misclassifications

Source: Original work by the author

not become overly reliant on automated feedback and continue to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

4.5 Legal and regulatory compliance

The deployment of automated grading systems must comply with relevant legal and regulatory frameworks, including data protection laws such as the general data protection regulation (GDPR) in the European Union (Parliament and of the European Union C, 2016). Institutions must implement robust data governance practices to ensure compliance with these regulations. This includes secure data storage, access controls and regular audits to verify that data handling practices meet legal requirements.

4.5.1 European rules on artificial intelligence

AI systems used in education, particularly those that evaluate learning outcomes or influence educational trajectories, are classified as high-risk systems (European Union Regulation, 2024). This classification underscores the significant impact such systems can have on individuals' educational and professional opportunities. Improperly designed or implemented systems may perpetuate biases and violate the right to education or lead to discrimination against certain groups, such as women, persons with disabilities or individuals of specific racial or ethnic origins. To mitigate these risks, it is essential to ensure that automated grading systems are designed with fairness, transparency and inclusivity in mind.

Automated grading tools should include mechanisms that allow instructors to oversee their functioning, verify their outputs and intervene when necessary. This oversight ensures that the system is used as intended and that its impacts are addressed throughout its life cycle. Instructors must receive proper training to understand the system's capabilities and limitations, enabling them to make informed decisions about when and how to rely on its outputs.

5. Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of the results

The results of the study highlight the effectiveness and challenges of using automated grading systems, particularly in the context of open-ended questions and grading technical reports.

In the context of RAG, the model demonstrated potential in generating relevant Q&A pairs, particularly for geotechnics, by leveraging a curated corpus of 26 geotechnics textbooks. This approach ensured that the generated questions and answers were accurate, relevant and aligned with current best practices. Additionally, the synthetic generation of student answers with varying quality levels enriched the data set, providing a robust foundation for training the ML-driven grading system.

In the analysis of grading open-ended questions using cosine similarity, the findings indicate that the approach struggles to achieve reliable performance, as evidenced by all metrics being below 0.5. While user answers generally exhibit some degree of

similarity to the correct responses, the confusion matrix (Figure 3) reveals significant misclassifications, particularly into Grade 4, suggesting a bias toward this grade. The highest performance was observed for Grades 4 and 2, but Grades 3 and 5 showed notably lower true positive rates, with Grade 5 having the fewest. These results indicate that the cosine similarity approach is insufficient for accurately distinguishing between grades, with frequent misclassifications and limited ability to handle variability in user responses.

The analysis of LLM grading shows a clear improvement in model performance with larger data sets, achieving around 98% across various metrics. This finding underscores the importance of diverse training data in enhancing the model's ability to generalise and accurately assess student responses. The examples provided illustrate the model's capability to differentiate between relevant, detailed answers and irrelevant or incorrect responses, indicating its potential utility in educational contexts.

The grading of real answers by the lecturer compared to LLM predictions reveals some discrepancies, probably due to unseen questions. The limited confidence of the LLM in grading certain responses suggests that the model may struggle with questions that differ from its training data. Even applying a minimum confidence threshold did not ensure reliable grading outcomes.

The incorporation of active learning strategies, as with the Web-app showcased, where the model interacts with users thereby collecting data, could further enhance its robustness and adaptability to real-world educational scenarios.

Finally, the evaluation of the dbmdz/bert-base-german-cased model for grading test reports yielded performance metrics that suggest the current approach is yet not ripe for practical use, but shows potential for further development.

5.2 Implications for the field of geotechnics

The implications of the study's findings for the field of geotechnics are significant, particularly in the context of educational assessment and the integration of automated grading systems.

First, the exploration of RAG for generating relevant educational content indicates that these technologies can be leveraged not only for assessment but also for content creation. This dual application can enhance the learning resources available to students, providing them with tailored materials that align with their coursework and industry standards.

Second, the successful application of automated grading systems suggests that these technologies can enhance the assessment of open-ended questions in geotechnics education. This is particularly relevant given the complexity and variability of student responses in this field. By providing a more objective and consistent grading mechanism, automated systems can help reduce the subjectivity often associated with human grading, thereby promoting fairness in evaluations.

Third, the study highlights the potential for continuous improvement in automated grading systems through the incorporation of diverse data sets. As the field of geotechnics evolves, so too do the standards and practices. Automated systems that can be updated with new data and feedback can ensure that assessments remain relevant and aligned with

current industry practices. This adaptability is crucial in a field where knowledge and techniques are constantly advancing.

The ability to provide immediate feedback on open-ended questions equips students with the opportunity to identify and address gaps in their understanding well before formal examinations.

Finally, the study's findings underscore the importance of ethical considerations in deploying automated grading systems. Issues such as data privacy, student consent and fairness in model training must be addressed to ensure responsible use of these technologies.

6. Conclusions and future work

This study explored the application of LLMs for automated grading and content generation in the field of geotechnics. By leveraging advanced NLP techniques, we aimed to enhance student assessment and educational content creation. The study involved the generation of synthetic questions and answers using a tailored generative pre-trained transformer model, the evaluation of real student answers using cosine similarity and the training and validation of an LLM for grading open-ended questions. Additionally, we attempted to use LLMs to grade technical reports. The results demonstrated the potential of LLMs to generate relevant educational content, provide consistent and objective assessments and assist students in self-assessment and learning.

The key contributions of this study are as follows:

- By tailoring LLMs with geotechnics textbooks and industry standards, we successfully generated relevant and high-quality questions and answers. The use of RAG further enhanced the accuracy and relevance of the generated content.
- We developed and validated an ML-driven grading system that uses cosine similarity and LLMs to assess open-ended questions in geotechnics. The system demonstrated the ability to provide consistent and objective grades, comparable to human graders.
- The automated grading system provides the potential for students to receive immediate feedback on open-ended questions, enhancing learning outcomes by allowing for the identification and correction of gaps in knowledge before formal examinations.
- The evaluation of the dbmdz/bert-base-german-cased model for grading test reports demonstrated its potential for automating the grading process but highlighted the need for further refinement to achieve practical applicability in educational settings.
- The study addressed important ethical issues, including data privacy, student consent, fairness in model training and transparency. By ensuring responsible deployment of ML technologies, we aimed to build trust and credibility among students and educators.

While the study demonstrated promising results, there are several limitations and areas for potential improvement:

- The accuracy and reliability of the automated grading system can be further enhanced by incorporating more diverse and representative training data. Continuous monitoring and fine-tuning of the model are necessary to address any biases and improve performance.

- The current reliance on cosine similarity for grading open-ended questions limits the system's ability to fully capture the nuances of student responses. Transitioning to a more advanced LLM-based approach requires collecting a larger data set of student answers to train and validate the model effectively.
- The interpretability of the LLM's decision-making process remains a challenge. Providing clear and transparent explanations for assigned grades is essential to build trust among educators and students and to ensure the system's outputs are understandable and actionable.
- The system's performance in grading technical reports was moderate, indicating the need for further refinement in handling complex, structured responses. This includes exploring alternative approaches, such as CNNs or visual transformers, to improve grading accuracy for such tasks.
- Ethical concerns, such as potential biases in the model and the need for human oversight, must be continuously addressed. Ensuring that the system adheres to ethical guidelines, such as those outlined in the EU AI Act, is critical for its responsible deployment.

Despite these challenges, the study demonstrates how ML-driven grading systems can fundamentally improve the way educational assessments are conducted in geotechnics.

Supplementary material

The supplementary material can be viewed at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17232530>.

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Appendix

Table A1 30 ChatGPT-generated geotechnics questions created using a RAG approach

No.	ChatGPT-generated question
1	Explain the difference between cohesive soils and cohesionless soils. Provide examples of each and discuss their engineering significance
2	A falling head permeability test is conducted on a silty clay sample. Explain the procedure and derive the formula for calculating the coefficient of permeability from the test data
3	In a direct shear test on a sandy soil, the shear load at failure was 135 N, and the normal load was 190 N. Calculate the friction angle of the sand. (Hint: Use the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion.)
4	Explain the concept of consolidation settlement in soils. How does it differ from immediate settlement and secondary compression? Provide examples of scenarios where consolidation settlement is significant
5	Describe the differences between the unconsolidated undrained (UU), consolidated undrained (CU), and consolidated drained (CD) triaxial tests. For each test, explain the conditions under which it is preferred
6	A standard Proctor compaction test was performed on a silty clay soil. Explain the purpose of this test and describe how the optimum water content and maximum dry density are determined
7	What is a borehole log, and what information does it typically include? Discuss its importance in geotechnical site investigations
8	Explain the concept of the factor of safety (FoS) in slope stability analysis. How is it calculated, and what does it signify in terms of slope failure?
9	What are the key differences between shallow foundations and deep foundations? Provide examples of situations where each type would be appropriate
10	Define the following terms and explain their significance in geotechnical engineering: void ratio, degree of saturation, effective stress, plasticity index
11	Explain the process of soil formation and differentiate between residual soils and transported soils. Provide examples of each
12	What is the significance of the Atterberg limits in soil classification? Describe how the liquid limit, plastic limit, and shrinkage limit are determined
13	Describe the procedure for conducting a standard penetration test (SPT). What is the significance of the N-value obtained from this test?
14	Explain the concept of effective stress in soils. How does it influence the strength and deformation behavior of soil?
15	What is the purpose of a flow net in geotechnical engineering? Describe the steps involved in constructing a flow net and its applications.
16	Discuss the factors that influence the bearing capacity of shallow foundations. How can the bearing capacity be improved in weak soils?
17	What is the difference between active earth pressure, passive earth pressure, and at-rest earth pressure? Provide examples of structures where each type of earth pressure is relevant
18	Explain the concept of liquefaction in soils. Under what conditions does it occur, and what are its implications for geotechnical design?
19	Describe the procedure for conducting a plate load test. How is the data from this test used to estimate the bearing capacity and settlement of a foundation?
20	What are geosynthetics, and how are they used in geotechnical engineering? Provide examples of their applications in soil reinforcement, drainage, and erosion control
21	What is the difference between total stress, effective stress, and pore water pressure in soils? How are they related?
22	Explain the concept of critical hydraulic gradient in soils. How is it calculated, and why is it important in preventing soil piping or heaving?

(continued)

Table A1

No.	ChatGPT-generated question
23	Describe the procedure for performing a hydrometer analysis. How is this test used to determine the grain size distribution of fine-grained soils?
24	What is the significance of the coefficient of consolidation in soil mechanics? How is it determined from a consolidation test?
25	Explain the concept of soil compaction. What are the differences between standard Proctor and modified Proctor compaction tests?
26	Discuss the role of soil suction in unsaturated soils. How does it affect the shear strength and permeability of the soil?
27	What is the difference between a cantilever retaining wall and a gravity retaining wall? Under what conditions would each type be used?
28	Explain the concept of settlement in pile foundations. What are the primary factors that influence the settlement of a pile group?
29	Describe the procedure for conducting a vane shear test. What are its limitations, and in what types of soils is it most commonly used?
30	What is the purpose of a geotechnical centrifuge test? How is it used to model and study soil-structure interaction problems?

Note(s): These questions cover a wide range of topics and complexity levels within geotechnics, ensuring a diverse dataset for training and evaluating the ML-driven grading system. Each question was reviewed by the authors to ensure accuracy and relevance

Table A2 Examples of ChatGPT-generated “correct” answers corresponding to the geotechnical questions in Table A1

No.	ChatGPT-generated “correct” answer
1	Cohesive soils, such as clays, have fine particles and exhibit plasticity, while cohesionless soils, such as sands and gravels, consist of larger particles and rely on friction for strength. Cohesive soils are significant in retaining water and are prone to settlement, while cohesionless soils are preferred for drainage and stability
2	The falling head permeability test involves allowing water to flow through a soil sample under a decreasing head. The coefficient of permeability is calculated using the cross-sectional area of the standpipe, the length of the soil sample, the cross-sectional area of the soil sample, the time, and the initial and final heads
3	The friction angle is calculated using the Mohr-Coulomb criterion. The shear load at failure and the normal load are used to determine the angle of internal friction, which represents the soil’s resistance to shearing
4	Consolidation settlement occurs due to the expulsion of water from soil voids under sustained loading. It differs from immediate settlement, which is elastic deformation, and secondary compression, which is due to long-term creep. Consolidation settlement is significant in clayey soils under structures like embankments and buildings
5	The unconsolidated undrained test is conducted without allowing drainage during consolidation or shearing, suitable for rapid loading conditions. The consolidated undrained test allows drainage during consolidation but not during shearing, used for intermediate loading rates. The consolidated drained test allows drainage throughout, suitable for slow loading conditions
6	The Proctor test determines the relationship between water content and dry density. The soil is compacted in layers at varying water contents, and the dry density is calculated. The optimum water content corresponds to the maximum dry density on the compaction curve
7	A borehole log records soil and rock layers encountered during drilling. It includes soil type, depth, groundwater level, and test results. It is crucial for understanding subsurface conditions and designing foundations
8	The factor of safety is the ratio of resisting forces to driving forces in a slope. It is calculated as the resisting forces divided by the driving forces. A factor of safety greater than one indicates stability, while less than one indicates failure.
9	Shallow foundations, such as spread footings, transfer loads near the surface and are used for light structures. Deep foundations, such as piles, transfer loads to deeper, stronger layers and are used for heavy structures or weak surface soils
10	Void ratio is the ratio of void volume to solid volume, indicating soil porosity. Degree of saturation is the percentage of voids filled with water. Effective stress is the stress carried by soil grains, influencing strength. Plasticity index is the range of water content where soil is plastic, indicating its plasticity
11	Residual soils form in place from weathering, while transported soils are moved by wind, water, or glaciers. Examples include laterite for residual soils and alluvium for transported soils
12	Atterberg limits classify soil consistency. The liquid limit is determined by the Casagrande apparatus, the plastic limit by rolling soil threads, and the shrinkage limit by drying a soil sample
13	The standard penetration test involves driving a split-barrel sampler into the soil using a hammer. The N-value is the number of blows required for the last 300 millimeters of penetration. It indicates soil density and strength
14	Effective stress is the stress carried by soil particles, calculated as the total stress minus the pore water pressure. It governs soil strength and deformation.
15	A flow net is a graphical representation of flow paths and equipotential lines in soil. It is constructed by solving Laplace’s equation and is used to analyze seepage and uplift pressure

(continued)

Table A2

No.	ChatGPT-generated "correct" answer
16	Bearing capacity depends on soil type, depth, and load. It can be improved by soil compaction, grouting, or using geosynthetics
17	Active earth pressure occurs when soil pushes against a structure, passive when the structure pushes against soil, and at-rest when there is no movement. Examples include retaining walls for active and passive pressures and basements for at-rest pressures
18	Liquefaction occurs in saturated, loose sands during dynamic loading, causing loss of strength. It is critical in earthquake-prone areas.
19	The plate load test involves loading a steel plate on the soil and measuring settlement. The data is used to estimate bearing capacity and settlement of foundations
20	Geosynthetics are synthetic materials used in geotechnics for reinforcement, drainage, and erosion control. Examples include geotextiles for soil stabilization and geomembranes for waterproofing
21	Total stress is the overall stress in soil, effective stress is the stress carried by soil particles, and pore water pressure is the stress due to water in voids. They are related by subtracting pore water pressure from total stress
22	The critical hydraulic gradient is the gradient at which soil particles begin to move. It is crucial for preventing piping and heaving
23	The hydrometer analysis involves dispersing soil in water and measuring sedimentation rates. It determines the grain size distribution of fine soils using Stokes' law
24	The coefficient of consolidation indicates the rate of consolidation. It is determined from the slope of the time-settlement curve in a consolidation test
25	Soil compaction increases density by reducing air voids. The standard Proctor test uses a 2.5-kilogram hammer, while the modified Proctor test uses a 4.5-kilogram hammer, resulting in higher compaction energy
26	Soil suction in unsaturated soils is the tension in pore water. It increases shear strength and reduces permeability
27	Cantilever retaining walls rely on the weight of the wall and soil for stability, while gravity walls rely solely on their weight. Cantilever walls are used for taller structures, and gravity walls for shorter ones
28	Pile settlement depends on soil type, pile length, and load. It includes elastic compression, end-bearing settlement, and shaft friction settlement.
29	The vane shear test measures undrained shear strength by rotating a vane in the soil. It is limited to soft clays and silts
30	Geotechnical centrifuge tests simulate real-scale soil-structure interactions by scaling down models and increasing gravity. They are used to study slope stability, foundation behavior, and earth pressures

Note(s): These answers were designed to serve as reference solutions for evaluating student responses

Corresponding author

Enrico Soranzo can be contacted at: enrico.soranzo@boku.ac.at

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